

Waste Water Management: Different Sewage & industrial effluents Water Clarification Using *Moringa Oleifera*

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Abstract:

The high cost of treated water makes most people in the rural communities resort to readily available water sources which are normally of low quality exposing them waterborne diseases. Water treatment facilities are designed to speed up the natural process of purifying water. With billions of people and even more wastewater, the natural process is overloaded. Without wastewater treatment, the amount of wastewater would cause devastation, as it still does today in developing countries. Globally, over 80 percent of all wastewater is discharged without in the countries that do have water treatment facilities, they use various methods to treat water with one common goal. During this study, sewage water sample were collected for treatment of moringa oleifera seed in powdered form. *Moringa oleifera* seed can be used as a natural coagulant. It is natural clarification agent for highly turbid and untreated pathogenic water. Various doses of moringa seed powder such as 50mg/ml, 100mg/ml, and 150 mg/ml were taken to check the efficiency doses of sewage water. After treatment with seed powder the sewage water were analyzed with various physical parameter like PH, turbidity, TDS, TSS, TS. PH was decreased at 50 and 100 dose, but it was increased at 150 dose.(7-7.5). Turbidity decreased with increased dose 50, 100, and 150. The TDS, TSS and TS are after treatment were reduced. After that three methods are carried out for comparison with natural coagulant *Moringa oleifera*. In physical method, the colony count was measured by colony forming unit. After this treatment, the number of bacterial colonies were reduced with increased dose of *Moringa* seed powder. In chemical method, the natural coagulant are compared with chemical coagulant like alum, charcoal and sodium chloride. After this comparison result show that chemical coagulant are more effective but the excess use of chemical coagulant are harmful to health. In biological method, the natural coagulant are compared with nonpathogenic microbes like *E.coli*, *S.aureous*, and *Pseudomonas*. After that BOD and COD were measured with respect to water samples. The calculated BOD value was greater than that of standard disposal value of sample require further treatment. And the COD is highly effective. COD removal efficiency was linearly increased up to the maximum dosage of *Moringa oleifera* seed powder used in various forms such as, 50mg/ml, 100mg/ml, and 150mg/ml. Application of this low cost *Moringa oleifera* is recommended for eco-friendly, nontoxic, simplified water treatment where rural and peri-urban people living in extreme poverty are presently drinking highly and microbiologically contaminated water.

Keywords: *Moringa oleifera*, waste water treatment, natural coagulant, chemical coagulant, non-pathogenic microbes (*E.coli*, *S.aureous*, and *Pseudomonas*), COD, BOD.

Introduction:

Water born disease are one of the main problems in developing countries, about 1,6 million people are compelled to use contaminated water. However in many communities of these countries water clarification methods like flocculation, coagulation and sedimentation are often inappropriate because of high cost and low availability of chemical coagulant. The use of natural material plant origin to clarify turbid water is not a new idea. Among all the plant materials that have been tested over the years, the seeds from *Moringa oleifera* have been shown to be one of the most effective as a primary coagulant for water treatment and can be compared to those as of alum (conventional chemical coagulant). *Moringa oleifera* was originally an ornamental tree in the sudan, planted during british rule. That was where Dr.samia Al azharia Jahn's (a german scientist) laboratory test confirmed the presence of a very efficient coagulant in seeds of *moringa oleifera* (1). The *Moringa oleifera* is a small, fast-growing, drought deciduous tree that ranges in height from 5-12m with an open, umbrella shaped crown, straight trunk(10-13cm thick) with corky, whitish bark. The evergreen foliage has leaflets 1-2cm in diameter; the flowers are white or cream coloured. The fruits (pods) are initially light green, slim and tender, eventually becoming dark green, firm and upto 120cm long, depending on the variety. Fully mature, dried seeds are round or triangular shaped, the kernel being surrounded by a lightly wooded shell with three papery wings. It tends to be deeply rooted, has a wide open typically-umbrella shaped crown and usually a single stem (2). *Moringa oleifera* contains many chemical compounds, such as vitamins, also secondary metabolites including vanillin, flavonoids, ferulic acids, gallic acids, ellagic acids, phenolic acids, chlorogenic acids,

glucosinolates, quercetin, also kaempferol, that have nutritional, antimicrobial and pharmaceutical properties. *Moringa oleifera* has wide range of bioactive compounds that obtained in different herbal structures such as leaves, stems, and shell. It consists of bioactive molecules, such as phenolic compounds (3).

Moringa oleifera has wide range of bioactive compounds that obtained in different herbal structures such as leaves, stems, and shell. It consists of bioactive molecules, such as phenolic compounds. The present study was carried out to confirm the effectiveness of seed powder extracted from mature-dried *Moringa Oleifera* seeds which are commonly in most rural communities. The main objective of this work is to evaluate the antimicrobial activity and efficiency of a natural absorbent from *MoringaOleifera* seed in treating river water. Herbal pharmaceutical industrial wastewater contain a high amount of suspended solid and alkaline ($\text{Ph}>8$); therefore it requires appropriate coagulant and flocculant compound for its wastewater treatment. *Moringa oleifera* can be easily established by cutting or by seed. Seeds can be sown either directly or containers and no seed treatment is required. The plants raised from 1m cutting beat pods from the second year and growth on wards with maximum production at 4 to 5 years. In a favorable environment an individual's tree can yield 50 to 70 kg of pods in one year (4). Generally, coagulants are used for (physical and chemical) purification of turbid raw waters. At very high turbidity the water can no longer be adequately treated by using filters. Coagulants have to be applied to transform water constituents into forms that can be separated out physically. In large scale treatment plants Aluminium sulphate is used as a conventional chemical coagulant. (5)

As an alternative to conventional coagulants, *Moringa oleifera* seeds can be used as a natural coagulant (primary coagulant) in household water treatment as well as in the community water treatment systems. Natural coagulant properties were found in 6 different *Moringa* species by laboratory studies. The seed kernels of *Moringa oleifera* contain significant quantities of low molecular-weight, (water-soluble proteins) which carry a positive charge. when the crushed seeds are added to raw water, the proteins produce positive charges acting like magnets and attracting the predominantly negatively charged particles (such as clay, silk, bacteria, and other toxic particles in water). The flocculation process occurs when the proteins bind the negative charges forming flocs through the aggregation of particles which are present in water. These flocs are easily to materials can clarify not only highly turbid muddy water but also water of medium and low turbidity. The level of turbidity influences the required time for the flocculation.as with all coagulants, the effectiveness of the seeds may vary form one raw water to another The most widely used flocculant is a synthetic that has certain problems such as non-biodegradability and release of toxic residual monomers. The use of eco-friendly flocculant as alternative materials for conventional flocculants in water and waste water treatment is increasing. Numerous factors influence the performance of coagulation–flocculation process, such as coagulants dosage, flocculant dosage, initial potential of hydrogen (PH) and velocity gradient of coagulation and flocculation.

Moringa oleifera seeds a promising resource for food and non-application, due to their content of monounsaturated fatty acid with a high monounsaturated/saturated fatty acid, sterols and tocopherols, as well as proteins rich in sulfated amino acids. *Moringa oleifera* seeds contain proteins that have activity coagulations

properties and are being used for turbidity removal in many countries. The quality of the treated water was analyzed and experiments were conducted on Different dosages of *Moringa oleifera* seeds. Determinations of PH, turbidity, hardness as calcium and magnesium, heavy metals and nutrient level were conducted before and after treatment with *Moringa oleifera* and other seeds. In this study, *Moringa oleifera* seeds were found better than other seeds in turbidity removal and had greater potential for water purifications than the other seeds tested. Raw water is essential before it can be disinfected for human consumption. In a water treatment works, this clarification stage is normally achieved by application of chemical coagulants which change the water from liquid to semisolid state. This is usually followed by flocculation, the process of gentle and continuous stirring of coagulated water. But for many communities in developing countries, however, the use of coagulation, flocculation and sedimentation inappropriate This Technical Brief gives an overview of application of an indigenous, naturally derived coagulant, namely seed material from the multi-purpose tree *Moringa Oleifera* Lam. (*M.Oleifera*) which offers an alternative solution to use of expensive chemical coagulants (2) .Chemical coagulants like Aluminium sulfate (alum), $FeCl_2$ Are used in municipal drinking water treatment plant for purification process. This excess use of amount of chemical coagulants can affect human health e.g. aluminium has also been indicated to be a causative agent in neurological diseases such as pre-senile dementia. In rural and undeveloped countries people living in extreme poverty are presently drinking highly turbid and microbiologically contaminated water as they lack of knowledge of proper drinking water treatment and also not afford to use high cost of chemical-coagulants.

To overcome chemical coagulants problems it is necessary to increase the use of natural coagulants for drinking water treatment. Naturally occurring coagulants are usually presumed safe for human health. Some studies on natural coagulants have been carried out and various natural coagulants were produced or extracted from microorganisms, animals or plants. One of these alternatives is *Moringa oleifera* seeds. It is of the sub-himalayan parts of north-west India. *Moringa oleifera* is a perfect example of a so-called 'multipurpose tree'. Earlier studies have been found *Moringa* to be non-toxic and recommended it to use as a coagulants in developing countries. The use of *Moringa oleifera* has an added advantage over the chemical treatment of water because it is biological and has been reported as edible. *M.oleifera* seed act as natural absorbant and antimicrobial agent as their seeds contain 1% active polyelectrolytes that neutralize the negatively charged colloid in the dirty water. These seeds are also act as antimicrobial agent against variety range of bacteria and fungi. The seeds contain number of benzyl isothiocyanate and benzyl glucosinolate which act as antibiotic. It is believed that the seed is an organic natural polymer. The active ingredients are dimeric proteins.

Moringa seeds possess antimicrobial properties reported that a recombinant protein in the seed is able to flocculate Gram-positive and Gram-Negative bacterial cells. (6) A general rule

of thumb is that the powder from one *Moringa* kernel to two liters of water is a good amount when water is slightly turbid, and to one liter when water is very turbid. The seeds and powder can be stored but the paste needs to be fresh for purifying the water.(4) The use of the local *Moringa oleifera* seeds for clarification is therefore useful in the purification of drinking water in developing countries, since other chemicals used in water purification are expensive. During this study surface water sample were collected for treatment by *Moringa* seeds in powdered form. Resulting in an effective natural clarification agent for highly turbid and untreated pathogenic water. Various doses of *Moringa* seed powder like 50,100 and 150mg/l were taken and checked for the efficiency dose on raw water. After treatment of seeds powder with water samples were analyzed for different parameter like PH, Turbidity, TDS, TS, Hardness, Jar test. Biochemical oxygen Demand (BOD), Chemical oxygen Demand. (1)

Materials and Methodology:

Collection of Samples:

The waste water was collected from different areas such as pharmaceutical industry, garbage area, Milk industry area which has collected effluents samples. The Waste effluents (sewage) water samples was being stored at room temperature. The *Moringa oleifera* were collected from local farming area near chh. Sambhajinagar.

Fig.1 Collection of Different Types of Sewage Samples (Industrial Waste Water)

Fig.2. Collection of *Moringa Oleifera* Leaf, Seed, Pod

Extraction of samples:

Moringa oleifera wings and coat from seed were removed. Fine powder was prepared by using mortar pestle and this powder was directly used as coagulant. Treatment to water was given by directly using seed powder. *Moringa* seeds contains fat by 0.1gm/100gm ingredients.

Fig.3. Fine powder of *Moringa oleifera* in different forms (pod +seed, seed, pod)

Aqueous extract of *M. oleifera* leaf was given orally at a dose of 100 mg/kg in rats. Fresh *Moringa oleifera* were air dried under room temperature until a constant weight was obtained powdered and extracted by soxhlet apparatus. The powdered seed of *Moringa oleifera* extracted with 10 volumes of 80% v/v methanol to obtain the methanolic extract.

Fig.4. Soxhlet Method (Extraction Process)

Physical parameters:

Sr. No.	Parameters	Methods
1	PH	PH Meter
2	turbidity	Nephelometer
3	TS	Evaporation
4	TDS/TSS	Evaporation
5	Colour	-

PH:

Treatment of *Moringa oleifera* seed powder was given to ground water samples in different doses. During the analysis, it was observed that after treatment with *Moringa* seed powder; PH was decreased at 50 and 100 dose, but it was partially increased at 150mg/l dose, PH was. After treatment the range of PH was 8-8.5 and the limit. The recommended acceptable range

of PH for drinking water specified by WHO is between 6.0 and 8.0. The treatment gave a PH range of 8 to 8.5 which falls within the reducing trends as the concentrations the dosing solutions were increased. The reverse was observed with the Moringa treatment. The PH increases with increasing concentrations of the Moringa as a

coagulant. It was reported that the action of *M. oleifera* as a coagulant lies in the presence of water soluble cationic proteins in the seeds. This suggests that in water, the basic amino acid present in the protein of Moringa would accept a proton from water resulting in the release of a hydroxyl group making the solution basic.

Table No.1: Before and after treatment of Moringa Oleifera seed powder show the different PH of sewage samples

Before treatment	After treatment of Moringa Oleifera seed powder		
Moringa Oleifera seed powder (0 mg/ml)	Moringa Oleifera seed powder Added in (50mg/ml)	Moringa Oleifera seed powder Added in (100 mg/ml)	Moringa Oleifera seed powder Added in (150 mg/ml)
PH 9	PH 8	PH 8.2	PH 8

Fig.5. Graphical representation of PH for sewage samples

Fig.6. Before and after treatment of Moringa Oleifera seed powder show the different PH of sewage samples

Turbidity:

The initial Turbidity observed was 12.4 NTU in ground water which was beyond the limits of WHO standards. It was observed that the use of *Moringa oleifera* seeds powder showed decrease in turbidity of ground water with increased doses at 50, 100, 150 mg/ml respectively. Residual turbidity reduces below 5 NTU. Due to this there was an improvement in the flock size and flock settled rapidly. The

overdosing resulted in the saturation of the polymer bridge sites and caused restabilization of the destabilized particles due to insufficient numbers of particles to form more inter-particles bridges. The high positive charge and small size suggest that the main destabilization mechanism may could be adsorption and charge neutralization. This was also reported by (madsen et al, 1987) and found that 90-99% of turbidity was removed by using *Moringa* seed powder.

Table No. 2: Before and after treatment of *Moringa Oleifera* seed powder show the different turbidity of sewage samples

Before treatment show the turbidity	After treatment of <i>Moringa Oleifera</i> seed powder show the turbidity		
0 mg/ml	50mg/ml	100 mg/ml	150 mg/ml
12.4	3.5	3.2	3.1

Fig.7. Graphical representation of turbidity for sewage samples

Total Solids, Total dissolved solids and Total suspended solids:

The initial TS was in range of 700-800mg/ml for ground water which was beyond the limits of WHO. In case TDS initial range was 600-700mg/ml above permissible limit. After the treatment *M. oleifera* seed powder, the total

dissolved solids were reduced from ground water. The range of total solids was found in between 350-500mg/ml and for total dissolved solid range was 200-350mg/ml.

TDS:

The filterable residue is the material that passes through a standard glass filter disk and

remains after evaporation and drying at 180 C.it is used to describe the inorganic salts and small amounts of organic matter present in solution in water. The principle constituents are usually calcium, magnesium, sodium, and potassium cations and carbonates, hydrogen carbonate, chloride, sulphate and nitrate anions.

Procedure:

The sample was taken and filtered out. Then, to initially weighted dish sample was added. The Dish was kept for evaporation in water bath. Final weight of dish was taken. Using these weight dissolved solids were calculated. Then, dish was taken in hot air oven at $182\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 hour. Dish was stored in desiccator until needed weigh immediately before use.

Fig.9.TDS Meter: (A) Before treatment (B) After treatment

TSS:

It refers to materials which are not dissolved in water and are non-filterable in nature. Also defined as residue upon evaporation of non-filterable sample on filter paper. Filter a well-mixed sample through a pre weighed a standard glass fiber filter and then dry the filter, and the residue retained on it to a constant weight. In a $103 - 105^{\circ}\text{C}$ oven. The increase in filter weight represents TSS.

Calculations:

Total Dissolved solids = weight of crucible with dissolved solids-weight of empty crucible. (5.90gm- 5gm= 0.9gm)
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Fig.8. After evaporation of sample show the TDS

Observation: In 50ml sewage sample, the total dissolved solid (TDS) = 0.9gm

Procedure: Various water sample was taken. Then, the concentration of water sample was checked with the help of TDS meter.

Procedure:

Volume of sample was measured and transferred into a glass dish. Washed sample with three successive volumes of $\geq 10\text{ml}$ reagent grade water. Complete drainage between washing was allowed and continue suction until all traces of water are removed. Filter was removed and dry it for 1 hour at $103-105^{\circ}\text{C}$ in hot air oven. Cooled it in a Desiccator to an ambient temperature and weighed.

Fig.10. Samples drying in hot air oven

Fig.11. Samples cooling in desiccator

Calculations:

Total suspended solids = weight of crucible with suspended solids - weight of empty crucible
 $= 0.36\text{gm} - 5\text{gm} = 4.64\text{gm}$

Observation:

In 50ml sewage sample the total suspended solid (TSS) = 4.64gm.

TS:

The materials left in sample vessel after evaporation subsequent oven drying at a defined temperature. Total solids includes both Total suspended solids and Total dissolved solids, which are physically separated via filtration.

Procedure:

A well-mixed sample was evaporated in a pre-weighed dish and dry it to constant weight at 103 - 105°C in a hot air oven. The increase compared to pre-weighed represents total solids.

Calculations

Total solids (TS) = Total suspended solids (TSS)
 + Total dissolved solids (TDS)
 $\text{TS} = 4.64\text{gm} + 0.9\text{ gm.} = 5.54\text{ gm.}$

Observation:

In 50ml sewage sample the total solids (TS) = 5.54gm/50ml.

Physical Method:

CFU (colony forming unit) - CFU means total colony count which is calculated by quantitatively. Due to high microbial load drinking water sample are unsafe for drinking purpose. Colony count was observed beyond the limit of USPH standard in ground water. The moringa oleifera seed powder treatment had an added advantage of reducing microbial load. After the treatment, the number of bacterial colonies were reduced with increased dose of moringa seed powder. Moringa Oleifera seed act as a antimicrobial agent against microorganisms.

Procedure: Sewage sample was added in each powder. Clear water was added in each powder as a control. Take optical density (OD) before and after at 600nm Then after filtration check

microbial growth and compare with sewage sample. Then, the cfu count was calculated by quantitatively.

Fig.12. CFU observed in different non-pathogenic microbes.
[Control, a) *Pseudomonas*, b) *S. aureus*, c) *E.coli* (more CFU count)]

Calculations:

- Plate number 1 : 56×10^{-4}
- Plate number 2 : 7×10^{-4}
- Plate number 3 : 108×10^{-4}

Result: After treatment, bacterial colonies were decreased with increasing dose of *moringa oleifera* seed powder. After the treatment the number of bacterial colonies were reduced with increased dose of *moringa* seed powder.

Chemical Methods:

Chemical coagulants like aluminium sulphate (alum), charcoal and NaCl are used in

drinking water treatment for purification process the excess amount of chemical coagulant can affect human health. To overcome chemical coagulants problems it is necessary to increase the use of natural coagulant for drinking water treatment.

A) Alum:

Requirements: Alum, Sewage sample.

Procedure:

Alum was taken with different percentage for the comparison. After filtration, optical density was taken at 600nm and compared with old sewage sample O.D

Table.No.3: Different sewage sample treated with chemical coagulant - Alum

Test Chemical coagulant- alum	Optical density (OD) of chemical coagulant-alum	
	Before	After
Water sample	0.04	0.01
Sewage water	0.07	0.05

B) Charcoal:

Requirements: Charcoal, Sewage sample

Procedure: Charcoal was taken in the form of warm powder. After filtration take Optical density

at 600nm and compare with old sewage sample optical Density.

Fig.13. Different sewage sample treated with charcoal

Table.No.4: treatment with chemical coagulant – charcoal

Test chemical coagulant charcoal	Optical density (OD) chemical coagulant- charcoal	
	Before	After
Water sample	Before	After
Clear water	0.04	0.02
Sewage water	0.07	0.0
Dairy water	0.06	0.03

C) Sodium chloride (NaCl):

Requirements: NaCl, Sewage sample

Procedure: NaCl was taken with different percentage for the comparison. After filtration take Optical density at 600nm and compare with old sewage sample O.D.

Table No.5: Different sewage sample treated with chemical coagulant -NaCl

Test Chemical coagulant- NaCl	Optical density (OD) of chemical coagulant -NaCl	
	Before	After
Water sample	Before	After
Clear water	0.04	0.02
Sewage water	0.07	0.02

Result: the chemical coagulant compare with natural coagulant and it is studied that, the chemical coagulant are more effective.

Biological Method:

Biological method take only for non-pathogenic microbes such as- *Bacillus*, *pseudomonas*, *fungus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *s. aureous*, *E.coli*. This microbes are compared with the *Moringa oleifera* seed powder for clarification of sewage water.

Requirements: Different microbial cultures (*E.coli*, *pseudomonas*, *s.aureous*), Sewage water sample

Procedure: Different microbial culture was taken in a test tubes with sewage water sample (*E.coli*, *pseudomonas*, *s.aureous*). The sample was centrifuge at 5000rpm for 10 minutes. Then supernatant was taken and Optical density was taken after 24 hours and 48 hours

Fig.14. Sewage sample treated with biological method

Table. No.6: comparatively study of natural coagulant and non-pathogenic microbes. Optical density after 24 hours.

Test (biological method)	O. D (biological method)
Control	0.0
E. coli	0.01
S. auerous	0.02
Pseudomonas	0.01

Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD):

Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) is the amount of dissolved oxygen needed by aerobic biological organisms to breakdown organic material present in a given water samples at certain temperature over a specific time period. The BOD value is most commonly expressed in milligrams of oxygen consumed per liter of sampling during 5 days of incubation at 20°C and is often used as a surrogate of the degree of organic pollution of water. BOD can be used as gauge of the effectiveness of wastewater treatment plants. It is listed as a conventional pollutant in the U.S clean water act. BOD is similar in function to chemical oxygen demand (COD), in that both measure the amount of organic compounds in water.

Requirements: BOD bottle, Sewage sample, Moringa seed powder

Chemicals: Ammonium chloride- 0.017gm, MgSo₄.7H₂O -0.825gm, CaCl₂ - 0.275gm ,

Manganese sulphate - 5gm, Ferric chloride- 0.0025gm, Sodium thiosulphate- 0.0016gm, Gram's iodine solution, Diluted H₂SO₄, Starch indicator- 0.5gm, Phosphate buffer-100ml, Glasswares.

Procedure: Water was aerated in glass container by bubbling compressed air for about 2 hours. The given sample was diluted by mixing it with appropriate amount of aerated at the level of 5% (40ml of sewage water in 10 ml distilled water). This mixture was distributed in BOD bottles. Then 1ml of each of phosphate buffer cacl₂, mgso₄, FacI₃, was added with continuous shaking in one BOD bottle. Brown precipitate was observed. This precipitate was digested by adding 2ml concentrated H₂SO₄. From BOD bottle 25ml A was taken. To this few drops of 1% starch solution was added and this solution was titrated against 0.025N sodium Thiosulfate. The end point of titration was blue to colorless. Similar procedure was applied for other bottles for one day up to 6 days.

(A) Sewage sample treated with sodium thiosulphate

(B) Blue colour appear after titration

(C) End point of test blue to colourless

Fig.14. BOD determine sewage samples

Table.No.7: BOD determined the different sewage samples.

Days of incubation (BOD)	Burette reading (BOD)	Dissolved oxygen in mg/ml (BOD)
0	5.3	9.2
5	1.3	4.8

0 Day

3 Day

5 Day

Fig.15. BOD determined the sewage sample with Moringa seed powder using BOD bottles

Calculations:

$$\text{DO} = \text{burette reading} \times \text{Normality of sodium thiosulphate} \times 8 \times 1000 \div \text{ml of sample} \times 40 - 10$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1) \text{ D.O-0 day} &= 5.3 \times 0.025 \times 8 \times 1000 \div \\ &25 \times 30 \div 40 \\ &= 31.8 \text{ mg} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2) \text{ D.O-5day} &= 1.3 \times 0.025 \times 8 \times 1000 \div \\ &25 \times 30 \div 40 \\ &= 7.8 \text{ mg} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{BOD mg/ml} &= (\text{DO-0day} - \text{DO -5day}) \\ &\times \text{dilution factor} \\ &= (31.8 \text{ mg} - 7.8 \text{ mg}) \times 50 \\ &= 24 \text{ mg} \times 50 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{BOD} = 1200 \text{ mg/ml}$$

Observation: The BOD of sample was found to be 1,200mg/ml.

Chemical oxygen demand (COD):

The organic matter present in sewage can be measured in number of ways. The oxygen required for chemical oxygen of organic matter present in given waste water by using oxidizing agent in acidic medium is determined by chemical oxygen demand (COD). Cod can be theoretically calculated if the organic compounds and their concentration are known. The oxygen demand of the sample can be accurately computed but it is impossible to know the details of organic compounds present in raw water or waste water. The cod is therefore determined by performing a laboratory test on given sample using a strong oxidant like acidic potassium dichromate.

Requirements: Sewage sample, Chemicals: potassium dichromate ($K_2Cr_2O_7$) – 0.06 gm, Ferrous ammonium sulfate – 0.09 gm, Mercury

sulfate, Silver sulfate – sulfuric acid solution, Ferriin indicator, D/W – 10ml

Procedure: 10 ml of sample was taken into a round bottom reflex flask. 2 ml of mercury sulfate was added into the flask and mixed by swirling the flask. 2 ml of potassium dichromate solution was added. Then 2 ml of silver sulfate – sulfuric acid solution was added slowly and carefully. 2-4 drops of ferriin indicator was added into the flask and titrated with ferrous ammonium sulfate (solution to the end point). Blank preparation of

the sample was made using D/W instead the sample. Reading was noted.

Table. No.8: COD determined the different sewage sample with moringa seed powder using COD bottles.

Test (COD)	Burette reading (COD)
Blank (D/W)	2.8
Sewage sample	7.9

(A) Sewage sample treated with Ferrous Ammonium Sulphate

(B) Reddish brown colour appear after titration

(C) End point of test colourless

Fig.16. COD determine different sewage samples

Calculation:

$$\text{COD as O}_2/\text{L} = (A - B) \times M \times 8000 \div \text{mL sample}$$

Where, A = ml sample FAS used for blank

B = ml sample FAS used for sewage sample

M = molarity of FAS

$$8000 = \text{milliequivalent weight of oxygen} = 1000\text{ml/l} = (2\text{ml} - 2\text{ml}) \times 0.098 \times 8000 \div 50\text{ml}$$

$$29.36 \text{ ml}$$

Observation:

The COD of sample was found to be 29.36ml.

Result:**Waste water of Pharmaceutical industry, milk industry, garbage area:**

In this study, the concentration of total solids (TS) of waste water are 5.54mg/ml. Average initial PH was 8-8.5 and settling time of sedimentation is 2-3 days. Moringa oleifera seed powder was used as natural coagulant for clarification of waste water. Moringa was extracted from local farming area. And this extracted Moringa seed powder was used to treatment of the waste water. The PH values were less than 8.5 or greater than 6.5. This proved that Moringa oleifera seed powder is not affecting PH values in the water samples. The initial turbidity was between the 12.7 - 4.0. The turbidity was reduced form water sample with treatment of seed powder. TDS increased from 353 to 410ppm and form 307 to 400ppm. This result show that, TDS was reduced with treatment of MO seed powder. TDS values were high in waste water samples. The TDS, TSS, TS are increased after treatment. The tree methods such as- physical methods, chemicals methods and biological methods for comparing with the natural coagulant Moringa oleifera seed. In physical method, the various microorganisms reduced with the incerasing dose

of moringa oleifera seed powder. In chemical method, the chemical coagulants are used in treatment of waste water like alum, charcoal, and sodium chloride. In comparison with natural coagulant the chemical coagulant are highly effective. But it is harmful to health. In biological method, the non-pathogenic microbes are compared with moringa oleifera seed powder. BOD was dramatically reduced after the treatment. 50% BOD was reduced after the treatment by *Moringa oleifera* seed powder. Regarding to DO, it improved from 2.58 to 4.00mg/ml. *Moringa oleifera* seed is directly proportional to Dissolved oxygen. Dissolved oxygen (DO) Value was between 3-5 mg/ml after the treatment. Therefore it is concluded that, MO seed has an important role in decreasing the DO value. COD of the waste water sample was 132.0 ± 2.83 mg/ml before the treatment, but increased to 164.0 ± 2.83 mg/ml after the treatment. This refers to high level of COD threats to human health. However, the overall treatment processes have been not affected by the increase of COD due to the natural coagulant used in wastewater treatment. MO seed is directly proportional to the COD.

Table.No.9: water analysis parameter for waste water sample treatment with Moringa oleifera:

Parameters of waste water treatment	Before treatment of Moringa seed powder	After treatment Moringa seed powder
PH	9	8 - 8.5
Turbidity	12.7	4.0
TDS	349	378
TSS	426	456
TS	871	834
CFU	108×10^{-6}	70×10^{-5}
BOD	2.58	4.0
COD	132.0	164.0

Fig.17. Different Sewage/effluents Water Treatment Using *Moringa Oleifera*

Discussion:

For waste water in pharmaceutical industry, milk industry, garbage area clarification of water quality parameters were analyzed after the treatment of various doses of *Moringa oleifera* seed powder. During this study, *Moringa* does not guarantee that the Raw water ends up completely (100%) free of pathogenic germs. It is cleaned and drinkable but not completely purified. Since, it reduces the number of suspended particles drastically. It also reduces the quantity of micro-organisms in raw water automatically. Also studied that, the *M. oleifera* seed powder reduced the turbidity .and in the treatment of seed powder with sewage sample the ph was increased. In this treatment, increasing the dose *Moringa* seed powder with increasing the turbidity and PH.The TDS, TSS, TS was reduced after the treatment of *moringa* seed powder.After that the physical method, chemical method and biological method are performed for the comparison with the natural coagulant *moringa* seed powder.BOD and COD are also increased with increasing the dose of *moringa* seed powder.

Conclusion:

Moringa oleifera seeds act as a natural coagulant, flocculant, absorbent for the treatment of waste water. It reduces the PH, total turbidity, TDS, TSS and TS.it also act as antimicrobial

active agent against the micro-organisms which are present in the drinking water and decrease the no.of bacteria. CFU was reduced after treatment of higher dose of 150mg/ml of *Moringa oleifera* .If a combined dose of *Moringa* seed powder and chlorine can give best result and waste water can be used for various purpose.*Moringa oleifera* seed is not giving toxic effect. It is eco-friendly and cheaper method of water treatment.

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